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Authors: Elżbieta Hryniewicka (NCN), Katarzyna Tabor (NCN)

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List of abbreviations

Abbreviation	Full form
AEI	State Research Agency, Spain
ANR	National Research Agency, France
CC BY 4.0	Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International license
CS	Call Secretariat
CSC	Call Steering Committee
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
DMP	Data Management Plan
DPO	Data Protection Officer
EC	European Commission
ESS	Electronic Submission System
EU	European Union
FAIR	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
JCA	Joint Controller Agreement
NCN	National Science Centre, Poland
OpenAIRE	Open Access Infrastructure for Research in Europe
OpenDOAR	Directory of Open Access Repositories
ODC-By	Open Data Commons Attribution License
PDDL	Public Domain Dedication and License
PDF	Portable Document Format
PID	Persistent Identifier
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
QSC	QuantERA Steering Committee
QT	Quantum Technologies
SAB	Strategic Advisory Board
UEFISCDI	Executive Agency for Higher Education, Research, Development and Innovation Funding, Romania

Definitions

Term	Meaning
Call Secretariat (CS)	Secretary body for the implementation of the QuantERA Call(s) comprising ANR, AEI and NCN
Call Steering Committee (CSC)	Decision-making body for the QuantERA Call(s) comprising representatives of the Research Funding Organisations participating in the Call(s)
Cascade Funding Calls	Mechanism for distribution of funds to research projects selected in transnational call(s) launched by QuantERA Programme
Coordinator (NCN)	QuantERA coordination & management body
Data Manager	QuantERA Coordinator representative responsible for the overall data management topics
Digital Object Identifier (DOI)	Specific type of PID, used to identify publications, datasets or other digital resources
Evaluation Panel (EP)	Internationally recognised expert in the field of Quantum Technologies who performs assessment of proposals submitted to QuantERA Calls
Management Board	QuantERA executive body responsible for the implementation of the Programme's work plan
Monitoring Secretariat	QuantERA body dedicated to monitor progress of research projects
Persistent Identifier (PID)	Unique, long-lasting reference to a digital resource
Programme Coordinator	Main Contact Person in NCN for QuantERA III Programme
Research Projects	Projects funded under QuantERA Calls
Scientific Advisory Board (SAB)	Scientific advisory body which consists of prominent QT researchers and industry representatives
QuantERA Consortium	QuantERA III Partners
QuantERA/ QuantERA Programme	Project funded by the European Commission under Grant Agreement No 101212998
QuantERA Steering Committee (QSC)	Decision-making body for QuantERA comprising representatives of the Research Funding Organisations being part of the QuantERA Consortium

Disclaimer

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1. Introduction

QuantERA III RIA: Cofund in Quantum Technologies under Horizon Europe is a continuation of its ERA-NET predecessors (QuantERA I and QuantERA II) under Horizon 2020. It aims at strengthening Europe's position in Quantum Technologies (QT) through a number of coordinated actions and wide cooperation with the key stakeholders. With 40 Research Funding Organisations (RFOs) from 30 countries, QuantERA's key activities are focused on funding quantum research and innovation through transnational calls. Along with organising and executing cascade funding calls, QuantERA implements additional activities including mapping and aligning policies, promotion of responsible research and innovation and fostering dialogue between academia, industry and policymakers.

This document constitutes the first version of Data Management Plan (DMP). Based on the official Horizon-Europe template¹, QuantERA's DMP serves as a framework for all data-related topics, with a focus on:

- The overall strategy for data lifecycle management,
- FAIR Principles,
- Necessary roles and resources,
- Appropriate levels of security,
- Ethical and legal considerations.

Following the Open Science² framework, for its public datasets QuantERA will use Zenodo³ as repository, in order to assure full compliance with the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable) Principles. Sensitive data will be stored in secure solutions, with full adherence to GDPR regulations⁴.

In view of the rapid changes in research environment and emerging new challenges, with this document QuantERA Consortium addresses the existing issues, at the same time acknowledging the need to have regular verifications and updates of its DMP.

2. Data summary

QuantERA III will both generate new data, as well as reuse the existing data, mainly from previous editions (QuantERA I and II). As the Programme is focused on coordination and administrative side of supporting cascaded funding, overall volume and types of data is expected to be of limited scope. As a result, the QuantERA III Programme will easily operate with existing structures and resources.

The initial identification of data expected in QuantERA III is presented in Table 1, with each dataset assigned a number (e.g., D#1, D#2). The same identification is used in Table 3, where the Role-Base Access Control (RBAC) is defined.

¹ See: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/temp-form/report/data-management-plan_he_en.docx

² For more information please visit: https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-research-and-innovation/our-digital-future/open-science_en

³ See: <https://zenodo.org/>

⁴ See: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/reg/2016/679/oj/eng>

TABLE 1. OVERVIEW OF QUANTERA III DATASETS.

Dataset #	Title	Type of data	Format	Estimated size	Dissemination level
D1	Reports - confidential	Documents and financial reports	PDF, CSV	60 MB	Confidential
D2	Reports – public	Standard office documents	PDF	140 MB	Public
D3	Promotional materials	Leaflets, posters, one-pagers	PDF	1 GB	Public
D4	Promotional videos	Audio-visual data	MP4	1 GB	Public
D5	Interviews	Audio data	MP3	100 MB	Public
D6	Surveys	Structured survey data	PDF, CSV	10 MB	Partly confidential
D7	Contact information (incl. SAB)	Lists	CSV	10 MB	Partly confidential
D8	Data from cascading grants – proposals & evaluation	Standard office documents	PDF, CSV	275 MB	Partly confidential
D9	Data from cascading grants – administrative and financial data	Documents and financial reports	PDF, CSV	50 MB	Confidential
D10	Data from cascading grants – research projects monitoring reports	Standard office documents	PDF	50 MB	Partly confidential

QuantERA’s expected datasets will be linked with Programme’s official deliverables defined in the Grant Agreement (reports, promotional materials, financial information), data used to facilitate collaboration with stakeholders (interviews and surveys involving quantum community and Scientific Advisory Board (SAB) members, contact list of involved Partners, SAB), and data connected with research projects funded under cascading grants (evaluation process including Evaluation Panel functioning details, selection and monitoring data). Each dataset will be stored in a solution with applicable access level, as described in Sections 3.1 and 6 hereof.

In the process of data lifecycle management, the following tools will be used to ensure efficient cooperation with the QuantERA Consortium and researchers applying for cascading grants:

- **Partner Area** – a cloud-based solution hosted by the QuantERA III Coordinator (NCN), with access restricted to the QuantERA Consortium partners. Its main purpose is to provide access to the key documents, ensuring smooth cooperation and efficient execution of the Programme. Data security is ensured by the authorisation procedure supervised by the Data Manager. In the case of incidents, additional support is provided by the NCN’s IT Team, as well as external web services provided. In both cases, appropriate procedures and regulations apply to ensure that an appropriate level of security and support is maintained.
- **Electronic Submission System (ESS)** – a tool hosted by QuantERA Call Secretariat Leader (ANR) for submission of proposals to the calls launched by QuantERA under its cascading grants scheme. All applicants are required to create and activate an account with an email address provided. To log into the system, a password authentication is required. Data is uploaded by respective members of the research consortia that apply for funding: Project Coordinator and Project Partners. Proposals consist of two parts: description of planned research (in PDF format) and financial overview (in .xls format). Submitted data is stored in a dedicated secure server-based ANR storage with real-time replication and an additional back-copy at the NCN.

- **UDiManager** – a tool hosted by UEFISCDI (Leader of a WP 4 concerning evaluation and monitoring), dedicated to recipients of QuantERA cascading grants. An online platform enables submission of monitoring reports at the mid-term and final project implementation stages, as well as project evaluation. The tool has been equipped with QuantERA module by the UEFISCDI Team during QuantERA I and since then has been maintained and updated according to the Programme’s requirements. UEFISCDI supervises any technical and organisational aspects (access, problems and incidents). Data is stored on Romania’s servers, with back-up versions of all reports at the NCN.

Due to the nature of the QuantERA Programme, data reuse will be limited to cases, where previously developed documents are updated or extended, e.g., as in the case of QuantERA III: “Task 6.4 - Mapping of Public Policies and Funding Instruments in QT”, which is a continuation of the mapping work under QuantERA I and II⁵. While working closely with the quantum community, QuantERA III will also make use of findings from strategic documents applicable to its scope (e.g., Quantum Europe Strategy released in July 2025, or the Quantum Act expected to be published in 2026⁶). In each case, the possibility of data reuse will be verified, based on the assigned license, with reference documents appropriately cited.

3. FAIR Principles

Following the key objectives of the Open Science framework, QuantERA’s aims to ensure that its data is FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Reusable). For each principle, specific adjustments will be made to match the nature of QuantERA actions and key topics, as presented in Figure 1. Additionally, QuantERA will promote the implementation of the FAIR approach within research projects funded through cascading grants. Dedicated guidelines regarding data management are laid down in Appendix 2 – Data Management Guidelines for QuantERA-funded projects , which will be shared with funded projects’ representatives.

⁵ Reports along with the exercise description are available at: <https://quantera.eu/mapping-of-public-policies/>

⁶ See: <https://digital-strategy.ec.europa.eu/en/library/quantum-europe-strategy>

FIGURE 1. KEY ASPECTS OF FAIR PRINCIPLES

3.1. Findability

To ensure compliance with the findability principle, all data for public access will be shared via [Zenodo](#). By using a repository registered in Directory of Open Access Repositories (OpenDOAR), QuantERA will benefit from its key aspects, i.e.:

- Unique and persistent identifiers (PIDs) – every upload will be assigned a DOI,
- Rich metadata – Zenodo’s metadata schema is compliant with version 3 of the OpenAIRE guidelines⁷,
- Use of DataCite servers - all data records contain DataCite’s mandatory terms, recognised as a widely accepted cross-domain standard.

QuantERA will ensure compliance of its naming and versioning rules with its internal procedures, in order to facilitate the process of securing traceability.

3.2. Accessibility

QuantERA’s general approach is to make data available whenever it is feasible. With strong emphasis on compliance with the Open Access principles, QuantERA datasets with dissemination level set to “Public” (D# 2, 3, 4 and 5 – as indicated in Table 1) will be deposited in Zenodo upon completion. At the same time, QuantERA will apply strict approach towards any datasets containing personal or sensitive data, including pseudonymisation, where necessary (e.g., for survey data).

⁷ See: <https://guidelines.openaire.eu/en/latest/literature/index.html>

Key aspects of making data accessible include:

- Data will be published under CC-BY 4.0 license, provided that no data protection issues have been identified,
- The target period of data availability is 5 years after the Programme's end date, with selected datasets accessible for 10 years (respective decisions will be made on a case-by-case basis),
- Metadata will be accessible even after the data itself is no longer available,
- Data will be made retrievable due to Zenodo's use of standardised communication protocols (OAI-PMH and REST API for metadata)⁸.

The expected volume of QuantERA III data is fully aligned with Zenodo's upload size limitations (50GB per record and up to 100 files⁹).

3.3. Interoperability

To ensure interoperability, QuantERA will use standard and widely recognised formats for data generated during the Programme, including:

- PDF – for deliverables and reports,
- CSV – for financial data,
- MP3 – for audio data (e.g., interviews, podcasts),
- MP4 - for audiovisual data (e.g., promotional videos).

Having chosen Zenodo, QuantERA will apply controlled vocabularies consistent with the FAIR Principles and secure qualified references to other data or metadata.

Where applicable (e.g., in the case of survey results), dedicated README files will be created to facilitate proper interpretation and correct use both inside and outside of the QuantERA Consortium. They will describe the general data structure, outline the methodology applied, and reference any related publications or datasets.

3.4. Reusability

QuantERA's data will be available for potential reuse owing to a number of activities and actions, i.e.:

- Open datasets with clear information that they can be reused with a proper credit given to its authors (text or graphic information on license CC BY 4.0 will be included in relevant materials),
- Details on data provenance for all datasets,
- Appropriate search keywords will be listed,
- Conducted interviews will have code books created,
- In the event of database development during QuantERA execution, applicable license will be assigned (e.g., ODC-By - Open Data Commons Attribution License).

Data management and stewardship within QuantERA will be led primarily by Coordinator, (NCN), which will ensure appropriate level of quality of all data-related activities.

⁸ For more information please visit: <https://about.zenodo.org/principles/>

⁹ See: <https://support.zenodo.org/help/en-gb/1-upload-deposit/80-what-are-the-size-limitations-of-zenodo>

4. Other research outputs

Due to the nature of the QuantERA III Programme, no additional research outputs are identified or expected in its course. In the event they will emerge, DMP will be updated accordingly, and appropriate procedures of data management will be applied.

5. Allocation of resources

Majority of activities listed in this document will fall under NCN coordination under WP1. Efforts from other QuantERA III Beneficiaries will also be part of general activities included in the Description of the Action within respective tasks and subtasks. Additionally, the position of QuantERA III Programme Coordinator will be combined with the role of Data Manager, responsible for supervising data-related processes and facilitating cooperation with the main QuantERA bodies (Call Secretariat, Monitoring Secretariat and Management Board).

Scope and volume of data generated in QuantERA III is expected to be limited, therefore, no substantial costs are envisioned for the purpose of data management. Data-related activities will be performed under the general budget of QuantERA III, with the use of existing infrastructure available within respective RFOs. Due to the limited size of expected data, Zenodo and potential use of pseudo-anonymization tools will be free of charge. The main resources linked with execution of QuantERA III are presented in Table 2.

TABLE 2. OVERVIEW OF MAIN TOOLS AND STORAGE SOLUTIONS.

Tools & storages	QuantERA Website with dedicated Partner Area	ESS - developed and maintained internally by ANR	UDiManager – developed and maintained internally by UEFISCDI	Respective institutional storage solutions
Organisation & responsibilities related to data	NCN – Coordinator & Data Manager overlooking all data-related topics & coordination of FAIR data management	ANR - Call Secretariat Leader – management of data from submitted proposals	UEFISCDI - WP4 Leader – management of monitoring and reporting from funded research projects	QuantERA III Consortium partners - general adherence to FAIR principles and data security rules
Envisioned costs and resources	Average cost of website hosting ~ 6 k EUR / year. No other direct costs related to data.	Cost of the tool operation included in budget for personnel expenses in WP3.	Cost of the tool operation included in budget for personnel expenses in WP4	Within general effort linked with QuantERA

For day-to-day operations, the QuantERA Consortium will use institutional storage solutions hosted by the Coordinator (NCN). Furthermore, respective RFOs will be in charge of storage and archiving of data applicable to the Consortium partners.

The overall objective for data preservation is 5 years after the end of QuantERA III. In specific cases, this period may be extended to 10 years, following a written recommendation from the QuantERA partners at a Consortium meeting.

6. Data security

Appropriate level of security will be ensured by a collaborative effort of all QuantERA Consortium partners. The key aspects of this task span 3 main areas, as described below.

6.1. Secure storage and back up

QuantERA data will be stored in line with the general requirements listed in the QuantERA III Grant Agreement and explained in more detail in the Annotated Grant Agreement¹⁰, to maintain the appropriate level of security, enable smooth collaboration within the Consortium and assure data availability. While for publicly available data Zenodo will be used (as described in Section 3), confidential datasets will be stored in respective institutions, mainly the NCN. This approach will grant support from the NCN's IT Team, with full scope of security measures, incident management procedures and general support in the case of any technical issues.

QuantERA backup strategy will be based on a 3-2-1 principle (three copies, two different media, one off-site). The key datasets will be stored on servers and cloud-based solutions hosted by the Coordinator (NCN located in Krakow, Poland), with additional copy stored by the ANR (located in Paris, France). For application data from the ESS hosted by the ANR, as well as monitoring and reporting data from the UDiManager hosted by the UEFISCDI (Bucharest, Romania), the off-site copy will be held in the NCN. In each case, a back-up solution will be in place (in line with respective local regulations) to limit the risk of potential data loss.

6.2. Access control

Access to QuantERA datasets will be granted pursuant to general rules applicable to the QuantERA Consortium partners. Access to confidential and partly confidential data will be provided either to all QuantERA III Consortium partners (which constitute QSC - QuantERA Steering Committee), or representatives of the RFOs participating in respective Calls launched by QuantERA (CSC - Call Steering Committee). The Role-Based Access Control to QuantERA's datasets is described in Table 3.

TABLE 3. RBAC IN QUANTERA.

Dataset #	Title	Dissemination level	Data host	Access
D1	Reports - confidential	Confidential	NCN	QSC
D2	Reports – public	Public	NCN	Unrestricted
D3	Promotional materials	Public	NCN	Unrestricted
D4	Promotional videos	Public	NCN	Unrestricted
D5	Interviews	Public	NCN	Unrestricted
D6	Surveys	Partly confidential	NCN	QSC
D7	Contact information	Confidential	NCN	QSC
D8	Data from cascading grants - proposals	Partly confidential	ANR	CSC
D9	Data from cascading grants – general administrative and financial data	Confidential	NCN	CSC
D10	Data from cascading grants - research projects monitoring reports	Partly confidential	UEFISCDI	CSC

¹⁰ See: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/common/guidance/aga_en.pdf

Access to respective data is given by data administrators from the hosting institutions. For datasets hosted by the Coordinator (NCN), all requests are approved by the appointed Data Manager who verifies them and approves the justified ones.

6.3. Personal data protection

Processing of all personal data in QuantERA is conducted in line with the GDPR and applicable national regulations from the respective RFOs. To assure appropriate level of control and cooperation, all QuantERA Consortium partners have signed the Joint Controller Agreement (JCA), which lays down a general set of rules to ensure security and transparency of personal data-related activities. As the QuantERA III Consortium includes members outside of the EU (Israel, Norway, South Korea, Switzerland, Türkiye and the United Kingdom), the JCA provisions introduce obligation to ensure similar levels of data security.

Other key information laid down in the JCA include:

- Data breach handling procedure, – including information on the approach and notification deadlines,
- Rules of potential transfer of data to third countries,
- Databases list – with defined purpose and means of processing,
- List of respective Data Protection Officers (DPOs) from all RFOs, including their contact details.

Furthermore, in order to ensure compliance with the applicable regulations, OpenAIRE's Amnesia¹¹ will be used for data requiring pseudo-anonymisation (e.g., surveys).

7. Ethics

As QuantERA focuses on funding transnational QT research projects, no direct ethical considerations are expected. Therefore, the focus will remain at ensuring appropriate conduct in relation to personal data collected and processed. Appropriate measures for granting informed consent will be introduced (e.g., for participation in the Evaluation Panel for the QuantERA Calls, interviews and surveys). In each case, participants will have all the privileges stemming from the GDPR, including the right to stop data collection or processing at any time, refrain from participation in certain segments of data collection, be granted access to all the personal data collected on them, with the option to correct or remove them.

8. Other issues & summary

QuantERA III aims to maintain the highest standards of its internal data management approach, as well as promote good open science practices among the beneficiaries of cascade funding. To facilitate both processes, additional materials have been prepared and annexed hereto:

¹¹ Tool available at: <https://amnesia.openaire.eu/>

- Appendix 1 – Data Management Guidelines for Consortium - key aspects of data-related topics for all QuantERA III Consortium partners, which complement the provisions of Grant Agreement, the Consortium Agreement, the Joint Controller Agreement and information from DMP's main body,
- Appendix 2 – Data Management Guidelines for QuantERA-funded projects - set of general guidelines for transnational research projects, supplementing information included in the Call documentation.

The QuantERA Consortium will continue to monitor data generated during the QuantERA III implementation, as well as new guidelines and recommendations, to ensure a holistic and effective approach towards data management. Close collaboration with all leaders defined in the QuantERA III Work Plan - Work Package Leaders and Task Leaders - will continue to ensure quality control of all data-related activities.

Appendix 1 – Data Management Guidelines for Consortium Partners

Data Management in QuantERA III - Guidelines for Consortium Partners	
	<p>Main documents connected with data management</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Data Management Plan - main document setting out the rules for the data lifecycle in QuantERA III ➤ Grant Agreement – applicable Horizon-Europe requirements ➤ Consortium Agreement & Joint Controller Agreement
	<p>Making data FAIR</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ✓ Findable – assign PIDs & rich metadata ✓ Accessible – use of open repositories & data retention ✓ Interoperable – proper format of data & README files ✓ Reusable – License & key words
	<p>Data repositories & tools</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Zenodo – used for sharing QuantERA public documents & materials. ➤ Amnesia – OpenAIRE’s tool for data anonymisation. ➤ Partner Area on QuantERA website – all documents relevant for QuantERA Consortium partners. ➤ ESS & UDiManager – systems used for proposal submission and monitoring of research projects.
	<p>Data security</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ 3-2-1 principle (three copies, two different formats, one off-site). ➤ GDPR adherence for all datasets with personal information. ➤ Role-Based Access Control – each new user submits request for access, which is approved by an authorised person.
	<p>Additional materials and reference documents</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ➤ Science Europe’s ‘Practical Guide to the International Alignment of Research Data Management’. ➤ Guidelines on FAIR Principles from GO FAIR initiative. ➤ OpenAIRE guide ‘How to comply with Horizon Europe mandate for Research Data Management’.
	<p>Contact details</p> <p>QuantERA Data Manager & Coordination Team: quantERA@ncn.gov.pl</p>
<p>Follow the Open Science mindset:</p> <p>“As open as possible, as closed as necessary”</p>	

Appendix 2 – Data Management Guidelines for QuantERA-funded projects

The QuantERA Consortium provides general guidelines for projects benefitting from the cascading grants. Information in this document is based on the EC requirements for projects funded under Horizon-Europe. Additionally, the beneficiaries of QuantERA must ensure full compliance with the rules set out by the respective Research Funding Organisations (RFOs).

1. Developing Data Management Plan (DMP)

- Creation of a DMP dedicated to a particular research project serves as a helpful tool in appropriate planning of activities and resources,
- A DMP should follow the official [EC template](#) – there is also a possibility to use tools dedicated to DMP generation (e.g., [Argos](#)),
- A DMP should be drafted and regularly updated, to outline the procedures for data collection, storage, sharing, and archiving in compliance with the FAIR Principles.

Key points	Data Management Plan
	Develop DMP for your project
	Verify & update DMP as needed

2. Access to data

- Open Access to publications
 - If possible, grant Open Access to all publications resulting from QuantERA-funded projects,
 - Deposit a machine-readable electronic copy of the published version or the final peer reviewed manuscript in a trusted repository at the time of publication,
 - Provide persistent identifiers (e.g., DOI) and rich metadata for publications and all related research outputs,
 - Disseminate results/outcomes of your research on open access platforms and repositories (e.g., [arXiv](#), [Software Heritage](#), [Zenodo](#), etc.),
 - Consider licensing publications under the Creative Commons Attribution International Public Licence (CC BY or equivalent) to maximise accessibility and reuse:
 - For monographs and other long-text formats, CC BY-NC or CC BY-ND licenses may be used to exclude commercial use and creation of derivative work, where appropriate.
 - Metadata for all deposited publications should be made openly available under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC0) and including comprehensive information, i.e. author details, publication venue, date, and Horizon Europe funding details,
- Data sharing
 - Making data open should in each case be done after consideration if data can indeed be publicly shared,
 - Before decision on sharing datasets, they should be checked if there is a need for anonymisation/ pseudo-anonymisation. Use relevant tools, e.g. [OpenAIRE Amnesia](#),
 - For databases, dedicated license should be assigned (e.g., PDDL or ODC-By).

Key points	Access to data
	Grant Open Access to publications, if possible
	Verify if data can be shared publicly
	Choose applicable data format, license and repository for your data

3. Compliance with FAIR Principles

➤ Compliance with FAIR Principles - making your data:

- **Findable** – data is stored in trustworthy repositories, described with rich metadata and PIDs (persistent identifiers) are assigned,
- **Accessible** – data is open, free and retrievable by using standard communications protocols. Metadata is accessible even if original data no longer is,
- **Interoperable** – data uses vocabularies, that follow FAIR principles and broadly applicable language for knowledge representation, README files are created,
- **Reusable** – data is assigned with accessible usage license and meets domain-relevant standards.

➤ Additional guidelines linked with FAIR Principles:

- Research data should be stored within repositories used by the quantum community, preferably registered in the Directory of Open Access Repositories (OpenDOAR),
- Details on data provenance and key words should be included to facilitate data findability and reuse,
- In each case, the applicability of respective license type to your datasets should be carefully verified,
- More information can be found at: <https://www.go-fair.org/>

Key points	Make your data FAIR
	Findable – rich metadata and DOI added to each dataset
	Accessible – no additional software required, standardised communication protocols are used
	Interoperable – appropriate format for access and processing
	Reusable – standard format of metadata and clear info on licensing

4. Data security & ethical considerations

➤ Data safety measures:

- Use the 3-2-1 principle (3 copies, 2 formats, 1 in remote location) – make sure your data is protected against intentional or unintentional loss or damage,
- Review the GDPR requirements for any personal data you will process during your project,
- Consider research security aspects (e.g., dual use).

➤ Ethics:

- At the beginning of the project, consider all applicable ethical issues and address them appropriately,
- Make sure you include ethical considerations in your procedures (e.g., informed consent in case of handling personal data).

Key points	Data safety & ethics
	3-2-1 rule to apply for back-up strategy
	GDPR should be followed for all personal data aspects
	Ethical and research security aspects should be considered thoroughly

Follow the Open Science mindset:
“As open as possible, as closed as necessary”